

Comparative analysis of genomic variants in two samples of *Escherichia coli* strain Nissle 1917

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1 Project Overview

The project comprises the variant calling and structural variants detection on two paired-ends whole genome sequencings of *Escherichia coli* corresponding to a unmodified sample of strain Nissle 1917 (EcN), named Sample_118, and a modified (gene integrated) sample of EcN (Sample_185).

2 Origin of the Data

Illumina genomic paired-ends FASTQ files for both samples were generated and provided by Macrogen, Inc (Seoul, Republic of Korea).

Genomic sequences of the inserts integrated in Sample_185 were provided in FASTA format by the user.

Reference genome for the analysis (*CP007799.1 E coli Nissle 1917*) was provided by the user in FASTA format. In addition, the user provided a FASTA file with the theoretical genome (manually created) of the modified sample Strain_185 (*EcN1917 cepa 185*).

3 Public Availability of the Data

Whole genome sequencing data have been deposited in the National Center for Biotechnology Information under Sequence Read Archive (SRA) accession SRP341149 (BioProject PRJNA770875, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA770875>).

Note to the user: that link will be publicly available when the BioProject becomes public. In the meantime, the link available for reviewers is: <https://dataview.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/object/PRJNA770875?reviewer=j52f1s5reife1fg0hk75n82v9k>

4 Analysis results

The output of this analysis includes this report, the external files used in the workflow (reference genome and annotation file), quality control and general statistics of each step of the analysis, the files containing the annotated variants called in the variant callings performed and the results of the structural variation detection.

5 Methods for variant calling of SNP and INDEL and comparison between samples

The analysis pipeline proceeds as follows for variant calling of SNP and INDEL:

5.1 Quality control of the reads

The quality of the user-provided FASTQ files was analyzed using FastQC v0.11.5[1]. The quality of the files was good. Only a minor issue (addressed in the next section) due to the presence of poly-G content was detected in a set of reads in the "reverse reads" file (_2) of each paired-ends sample.

FastQ Screen v0.14.1 [2] did not detect unexpected contamination with extraneous genomic material.

5.2 Trimming and filtering of reads

This step addressed the described issue of the presence of poly-G content in a number of reads. *fastp* software [3] was applied with the options `-trim_poly_g -poly_g_min_len 12`, that removes the final poly-Gs chunk of length 12 nt or more. Additional parameter `-l 50` filtered out reads of less than 50 nt long.

5.3 Alignment

Filtered sequences of both samples were aligned with BWA sampe (version 0.7.17)[4] against the assembly ASM71459v1 (GenBank sequence CP007799.1) for *Escherichia coli* strain Nissle 1917 with default parameters.

samtools version 1.11 [5] was used to compress the alignment files (SAM to BAM format), sort by coordinates and index the files.

Optical duplicated reads were removed using *Picard MarkDuplicates* version 2.18.26-SNAPSHOT [6] using the parameter `REMOVE_SEQUENCING_DUPLICATES=true`. `CREATE_INDEX=true`, `VALIDATION_STRIGENCY=LENIENT` and `ASO=coordinate` were also used.

Statistics and quality of the alignments were assessed for all samples with *Qualimap*[7] software (version v.2.2.1), *samtools* options `flagstats` and `idxstats` and *bcftools* (version 2.4.0) option `stats`. A summary of the statistics is displayed in Fig. 1. As observed, most of the reads were mapped to the reference genome and the mean coverage was very high (around 600X) and distributed evenly, with more than 98% of the genome covered by 50 or more reads.

Alignment stats

Sample_id	phenotype	Total Reads	Filtered Reads	Mapped Reads	Mapped after duplicates removal	Mean mapping quality	Mean Coverage Data	Percentage covered >1X	Percentage covered >50X
Sample_118	Control	23,674,286	22,929,560 (96.85%)	22,879,637 (99.78%)	22,524,313	55.0862	623X	99.64%	98.75%
Sample_185	Modified	22,312,866	21,742,722 (97.44%)	21,677,157 (99.70%)	21,346,635	55.0971	591X	99.47%	98.51%

Figure 1: Alignment statistics

5.4 Variant calling

Mapped reads (without optical duplicates) of Strain_118 and Strain_185 were the input of the *freebayes*[8] variant caller to extract SNP, INDEL,

MNP¹ and "complex"² events, with arguments `-pooled-continuous`, that also considers alternative models different from haploid, and `-C=5`, that filters out detected callings having less than 5 reads supporting the variant allele. In addition, `vcffilter` [9] with `-Q>20` was used to keep only variants having a probability that the site has a real variant (QUAL) of 20 or more.

The resulting multisample VCF file contained 316 variants respect to the reference genome: 153 deletions, 103 SNP, 22 insertions, 7 MNP and 31 complex events. All the called variants were present in both samples except two deletions, that are exclusive of Sample_118 (located in positions 4982169 and 4982544, within a region corresponding to one inserted sequence in Sample_185). No exclusive variants were detected for the modified sample, Sample_185.

5.5 Variants Annotation

The file with the 316 called variants was annotated using SnpEff[10] version 4.3t, with the option `-ud 500` and using a built database for *Escherichia coli* strain Nissle 1917. For user readability, in addition to the annotated VCF yielded by the SnpEff software, a tabular (.xlsx) file was generated with the called variants and their annotations.

5.6 Variant calling analysis using as reference an artificial genome comprising the inserted sequences

To check the existence of possible variants in the inserted regions in the sequenced Sample_185 respect to the expected sequence of that inserts, an additional variant calling analysis was performed aligning the filtered FASTQ sequences of Sample_185 (section 5.2) against an artificial reference file containing the FASTA sequences of the three regions inserted in Sample_185 (named *FlhDC*, *lux* and *mKATE*), plus 100 nt upstream and downstream of the inserts.

The alignment and the variant calling steps were performed using the same software and parameters described in the previous sections.

This variant calling yielded 6 variants in Sample_185, all of them in the *lux* inserted region: 4 SNP, 1 MNP and 1 insertion. Fig. 2 displays the called variants, all of them homozygous having a very good coverage and correct allelic frequency.

6 Structural variation detection

6.1 CNV-seq

We used CNVseq[11] to extract Copy Number Variation (CNV) between samples. We ran the script `cnv-seq.works.hliang.pl` provided at <https://github.com/hliang/cnv-seq> with parameters `-test`

¹A multiple nucleotide polymorphism with alleles of common length > 1, for example AAA/TTT

²No simple or well defined DNA mutation

Region	Position	Reference	Alternative	Calling Quality (freebayes)	Genotype	Depth	Depth Ref Allele	Depth Alt Allele
Region_lux	2128	GC	CG	17017.3	1/1	537	0	534
Region_lux	4085	A	G	16002.9	1/1	509	0	507
Region_lux	4220	T	G	14829.7	1/1	490	2	488
Region_lux	4226	G	A	15258.1	1/1	479	0	478
Region_lux	4452	CTTTTAC	CTTTTAC	13180.1	1/1	488	0	479
Region_lux	5902	C	T	13965	1/1	446	0	445

Figure 2: Variants found in Stain_185 when comparing with the theoretical sequence of the inserted regions

Sample_185.hits -ref Sample_118.hits -log2 0.9 -p 0.000001 -bigger-window 2 -annotate -minimum-windows 8.

The result was a set of three differential CNVs that match with the regions where the three insertions were placed. The value of $\log_2(\text{Sample}_{185}/\text{Sample}_{118})$ is strongly negative in the three cases (Fig. 3), corresponding to deletions (much more copies in Sample_118 than in Sample_185) of these regions in Sample_185. This is the expected output, as these regions of the reference genome are only in Sample_118. No additional unexpected differential CNVs were retrieved.

cnv	chromosome	start	end	size (bases)	$\log_2(S185/S118)$	p.value
CNVR_1	CP007799.1	383635	384246	612	-5.524645	0
CNVR_2	CP007799.1	2103787	2104074	288	-4.352368	0
CNVR_3	CP007799.1	4981447	4989114	7668	-8.953411	0

Figure 3: differential CNV regions between Sample_118 and Sample_185 detected by CNVseq

6.2 bedtools genomecov + intersect

bedtools genomecov [12] with parameters *-bga -split* plus *grep* filtering were used on the BAM alignment files to obtain the regions having no coverage of reads in each of the two samples. Then, we extracted with *bedtools intersect* those regions without coverage that are present exclusively in one sample and in the other. 7 chunks of >10nt having no coverage exclusively in Strain_185 and 4 chunks (>10nt) with no coverage only in Strain_118 were extracted. Visual inspection of these genomic regions with the genomic browser IGV [13] showed only 3 chunks as reliable in Strain_185 and none in Strain_118. These three chunks detected as deletions in Strain_185 (Fig. 4) are practically identical to the retrieved as differential in the CNVseq analysis.

Chromosome	Start_pos	End_pos	Length	Read Coverage
CP007799.1	383660	384263	603	0
CP007799.1	2103813	2104115	302	0
CP007799.1	4981490	4989159	769	0

Figure 4: Regions with no read coverage found exclusively in Sample_185 (bedtools coverage + visual inspection with IGV)

7 References

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